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Supply Chain Management With Reference To Pharmaceutical Industries In India

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Abstract

The Supply Chain Management is not a chain of businesses with one-to-one or business-to-business relationships, but a network of multiple businesses and relationships. SCM offers the opportunity to capture the synergy of intra- and intercompany integration and management. In that sense, SCM deals with total business process excellence and represents a new way of managing the business and relationships with other members of the supply chain. The supply chain not only includes the manufacturer and its suppliers, but also transporters, warehouses, retailers, and consumers themselves. It includes, but is not limited to, new product development, marketing, operations, distribution, finance, and customer service (Chopra and Meindl, 2001). Supply Chain Management (SCM) is “a set of methods used to effectively coordinate suppliers, producers, depots, and stores, so that commodity is produced and distributed at the correct quantities, to the correct locations, and at the correct time, in order to reduce system costs while satisfying service level requirements. The fundamental notion of the SCM is that a Supply Chain must be controlled in order to be fast and trustworthy, cost-effective, and flexible enough to meet customers’ requirements (Simchi-Levi, D., Kaminsky, P. & Simchi-Levi, E. 2003). SCM varies on the basis of the product, this article describe how the pharma companies maintain the SCM more effectively and how they try to manage cost effective methods.

Keywords: supply chain management, supply chain, logistics, pharmaceutical Industry, transportation.

Introduction

Supply chain management is defined as the systemic, strategic coordination of the traditional business functions and the tactics across these business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain, for the purposes of improving the long-term performance of the individual companies and the supply chain as a whole (Mentzer et al., 2001). The Global Supply Chain Forum define: Supply Chain Management is the integration of key business processes from end user through original

suppliers that provides products, services, and information that add value for customers and other stakeholders and it identified eight key processes that make up the core of supply chain management i.e. Customer relationship management, customer service management, demand management, order fulfillment, manufacturing flow management, procurement, product development and commercialization, and returns. Oliver and Weber (1982) introduced the concept of Supply Chain Management (SCM) in the field of logistics literature in 1980's. The concept of "supply chain" is well established in the literature and is generally referred to as the alignment of firms that bring products or services to market (Lambert, Stock and Ellram, 1998). The supply chain includes manufacturer, suppliers, transporters, warehouses, wholesalers, retailers, other intermediaries and even customers themselves. "Logistics - or supply chain management - is the function responsible for the transport and storage of materials on their journey from original suppliers, through intermediate operations, and to final customers" Waters (2008). SCM is the integrated planning, co-ordination and control of all business processes and activities in the supply chain to deliver superior consumer value at less cost to the supply chain as a whole whilst satisfying requirements of other stakeholders in the supply chain. Fundamentally, the pharmaceutical industry is a business that is about health and people. The pharmaceutical and healthcare industry is hugely complex because it involves so many markets, products, processes and intermediaries Whewell (2009). It is also globally heavily regulated and used by everyone in life. Changes in one area impact upon the others and environmental factors such as pricing, regulatory change or actions by competitors, influence the whole supply chain.

Review of Literature

Supply Chain is "a structured manufacturing process wherein raw materials are transformed into finished goods, then delivered to end customers" Beamon B. (1998). Supply Chain is the group of manufacturers, suppliers, distributors, retailers and transportation, information and other logistics management service providers that are engaged in providing goods to consumers. A Supply Chain comprises both the external and internal associates for the corporate, Chow, D. and Heaver, T. (1999). Bridgefield Group (2006) defines Supply Chain as "a connected set of resources and processes that starts with the raw materials sourcing and expands through the delivery of finished goods to the end consumer". Supply Chain management is aimed at examining and managing Supply Chain networks. The rationale for this concept is the opportunity (alternative) for cost savings and better customer service. An important objective is to improve a corporate's competitiveness in the global

marketplace in spite of hard competitive forces and promptly changing customer needs (Langley, C., Coyle, J., Gibson, B., Novack, R. and Bardi, E., 2008). SCM is vital for companies, as a successful SCM strategy can lower expenses and increase sales for the company. SCM practices enable the world's leading organizations to realign their supply chain to the distinct set of concepts by providing functioning solutions for enterprise needs in supply and demand planning and forecasting, sourcing and procurement, and supply chain execution (Susarla & Karimi, 2012). The Supply Chain Management Professionals' Council (2009) defines Supply Chain management (SCM) as designing and management of all activities involved in sourcing and purchasing, transformation, and all logistics management activities. Principally, it also includes coordination and partnership with network partners, which can be suppliers, mediators, third party service providers and customers. Fundamentally, Supply Chain management (SCM) coordinates supply and demand management within and across corporate. A well-managed and well-designed distribution system in pharma industry will have the features such as sustain a constant supply of medicines, maintain medicines in good condition throughout the process, minimize loss due to expiration and damage, maintain correct inventory records, utilize available transportation resources efficiently, provide information to determine forecasting medicine needs, and integrate a quality assurance program. The distribution process begins when the manufacturer ships the medicine and ends when the medicine consumption report is back to the procurement entity (Susarla & Karimi, 2012).

Indian Pharmaceutical Industry – An Overview

Indian pharmaceutical industry supplies over 50 percent of global demand for various vaccines, 40 percent of generic demand in the US and 25 percent of all medicine in UK. India accounts for 20 percent of global exports in generics. India's pharmaceutical exports stood at US \$17.27 billion in 2017-18 and are expected to reach US \$20 billion by 2020. The country's pharmaceutical industry is expected to expand at a CAGR of 22.4 percent over 2015–20 to reach US \$55 billion. India is the second largest contributor of global biotech and pharmaceutical workforce. Indian healthcare sector, one of the fastest growing sectors, is expected to cross US \$372 billion by 2022. The domestic generics market is expected to reach US \$27.9 billion by 2020. India's generics market has immense potential for growth. Indian pharmaceutical companies received record 300 generic drug approvals in USA during 2017 where the generic market is expected to reach US \$88 billion by 2021. By 2024-25, India's biotech industry is estimated to increase to US \$100 billion. By 2020, India is expected to

capture 6 percent to 7 percent of a \$760 billion global generics market. The Indian pharmaceutical market now stands at \$30 billion, with the highest number of sites approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) after the United States – a clear indicator of the important role Indian companies play in both local and global markets and the growing appetite to invest in the country.

Indian pharmaceutical industry wants to become a global supply hub, not only for the advanced markets but for the emerging nations and the rest of the world. There have been a lot of internal and external challenges today for Indian pharma industry, more from the external point of view when you look at global scrutiny, which is happening more from the regulatory agencies, the quality issues which are there, happening everywhere, not only in India but also throughout the world. Indian pharma industry are looking at supply chain cost, because when look at comparing ourselves to the global industry, there is a gap, so Indian pharma industry have quality, regulatory scrutiny, supply chain issues like increased supply chain cost and response of delivery teams to the patients in time and also inventory levels. These three issues are increasing the cost of supply chain and that is one of the very important factors where India needs to take corrective action right now if it has to become global and compared with best in class pharma companies because they are the leaders when supply chain is concerned.

Advantages To Indian Pharma Industries

Low cost of production and R&D boosts efficiency of Indian pharma companies, leading to competitive exports. Indian pharma exports reached US\$ 17.27 billion in FY18.

- India's cost of production is approximately 33 per cent lower than that of the US.
- India's ability to manufacture high quality, low priced medicines, presents a huge business opportunity for the domestic industry.

Indian Pharma Export Scenario

India is the world's largest provider of generic medicines; the country's generic drugs account for 20 percent of global generic drug exports (in terms of volumes). Indian drugs are exported to more than 200 countries in the world, with the US as the key market.

- Indian pharma companies are capitalizing on export opportunities in regulated and semi-regulated markets.
- Pharmaceutical exports from India, which include bulk drugs, intermediates, drug formulations, biological, Ayush & herbal products and surgical reached US \$17.27 billion in FY18 and US\$ 12.29 billion in FY19 (uptoNovember2018).

- The biggest export destination for Indian pharma product is the US. In FY18, 31 percent of India's pharma exports were to the North America, followed by 19.4 percent to Africa and 15.9 percent to the European Union.

Pharmaceutical Supply Chain Management

Supply chain in the pharmaceutical industry starts right from the raw materials procurement to testing of materials, getting it manufactured in facilities, storing it rightly at the manufacturing sites at the right temperature, at the right conditions and making supply chain responsive as far as this material delivery is concerned from logistics point of view. That is moving them from warehousing to distributors to stockiest, to hospitals or the retailer and finally to the patient. There are three key performance indicators that organizations rely on to gauge their overall supply chain management.

Customer Service – Big or small, pharmaceutical companies strive to ensure their products are available across the entire supply chain. Maintaining product quality also ensures good service levels. Best in class pharma companies in India operates at a 95 percent service level which is 4.5 points lower than best in class global pharma companies.

Inventory Levels – Fragmentation has resulted I large number of stocking locations. India has a multitier distribution network through clearing and forwarding agents and stockiest, because of long manufacturing lead times and regulatory requirements, pharma companies usually maintain higher stock levels than other industries, even at the cost of writing off expired inventory. Looking at the pharma industry as a whole, the average inventory level is 98 days higher than India's best in class.

Supply Chain Cost- supply chain costs depends heavily on the type of product. Specialized cold chain requirements for vaccines and other complies formulations can significantly increase supply chain cost. India's best in class pharma is 8 percent points higher than best in class global pharma. However, the industry average s 15 percent points higher than the global best in class, which indicates suboptimal routes, high transportation costs and issues with storage, specifically for high risk and conditioned products. On average, manufacturing conversion costs accounts for nearly 75 percent of total supply chain cost, with distribution responsible for the remainder.

PHARMACEUTICAL SUPPLY CHAIN MODEL

The overall the supply chain in the pharmaceutical industry, starts at the procurement and manufacturing industry so, industry should ensuring a control on the availability of raw materials and also active pharmaceutical ingredients which are basic drugs to ensure that full control on the availability. The next stage is warehousing. Whether it is warehouses within the pharmaceutical industry or external warehouses, these are created to ensure that materials are distributed from these large warehouses across India. Another stage from the distributor onwards is when the material reaches the stockiest and the retailers, whether it is stored well at the prescribed storage conditions or not. It has to increase monitoring and enforcement to ensure that the right quality reaches patient. In using this, it needs to ensure that to use a right network of good suppliers, good vendors, good partners in the good distribution practices.

Supply Chain Challenges For Indian Pharma Industries

Quality and Regulatory Issues – quality continues to be a important issue in India's pharmaceutical industries, with greater scrutiny coming from global regulatory agencies. Large and small pharmaceutical companies have taken a hit in FDA's concern about quality.

In the domestic market, the Central Drug Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO) has increased the coverage and frequency of inspections to address the issue of low-quality drugs.

Product Proliferation – new product development, new dosage forms, enhanced formulations and changes in packaging and labeling to cater to new markets are expanding the product portfolio. Leading Indian players launch anywhere from 15 to 30 products a year. This has several implications for the supply chain, including higher manufacturing and distribution costs, core inventory and a larger supplier base. Several underlying factors contributes to the product proliferation is changing consumer demographics, increased competition, varying regulatory requirements cross export markets.

Supply Chain Fragmentation – India’s pharmaceutical value chain is very complex and in some parts even poses concerns about product quality and safety, causing multiple repercussions. The sheer number of player’s in each stage and the lack of integration across the network have an impact in visibility and traceability of products as they move.

Infrastructure Gaps

India faces many gaps in its supply chain infrastructure, including in transportation, storage and power supply. In transportation less than 5 percent of roads are national highways and they handle more than one-third of traffic. The rail network is also inadequate, and the air network is underutilized. Drugs have varying storage requirements to ensure that potency is maintained throughout the shelf life. Moving specially product and vaccines required continuous monitoring at all stages of the value chain. But the current infrastructure, companies are still unable to ensure a product is stored at the required conditions throughout its transition.

Customer Service Level

Pharmaceutical companies in India strive to ensure their products are available across the entire supply chain. Maintaining product quality also ensures good service levels. Best in class pharma companies in India operates at a 95 percent service level, which is 4.5 percent lower than best in class global pharma companies. It would be challenging for Indian pharma companies to meet the service levels in the near term, the industry average is almost 7 points lower than best in class, indicating potential headroom for integrating the supply chain over the long term.

Indian Pharma Companies Service Level

Source: A. T. Kearney Analysis

Conclusion

Supply Chains are a critical part of world trade. However, a Supply Chain in itself is insufficient. Only those that are efficient will succeed. In consideration of a Supply Chain to be efficient, it is crucial to understand its principal functions as well as the role played by each function in the Supply Chain's overall efficiency. Accomplishing this makes it facile to identify obstacles and impact the essential improvements. To realize their full supply chain potential, India's pharma companies will need to revamp the models and processes. A supply chain transformation will be essential. This comprehensive change will require commitment from top management, coupled with a capable execution team that can help sustain the benefits. Although this is no small task, this is the time for pharma companies to follow suit and prepare for the future. Those that lead the way will capture a competitive advantage.

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